

RATING CRITERIA FOR SPEAKING TASKS

	OVERALL PROFICIENCY (overall oral production)	Range	Accuracy	Fluency	Pronunciation
Pre-A1	Can produce short phrases about themselves and daily routines, using short, formulaic expressions.	Can describe themselves (e.g., name, age, family), using simple words and formulaic expressions. Can express how they are feeling using some simple adjectives.	Can use some very simple grammatical structures and sentence patterns from a memorised repertoire.	Can manage some short, isolated, rehearsed utterances, but needs time to prepare and think. Speech contains many long pauses, repetitions, and breaks.	Can produce a very limited range of the most common sounds and expressions in a way that is understandable.
A1	Can describe simple aspects of their everyday life using simple words and basic phrases.	Has a very basic range of simple expressions related to personal details and concrete needs. Can describe themselves, what they do and where they live.	Shows limited control of a few simple grammatical structures and sentence patterns.	Can manage short, isolated utterances, with much pausing to search for expressions, to articulate less familiar words, and to repair communication.	Pronunciation of a very limited repertoire of learnt words and phrases can be understood with some effort by an interlocutor used to dealing with speakers of the language group concerned. Can reproduce correctly a limited range of sounds as well as stress on simple, familiar words and phrases.
<p>A1 > A2: The speech is more continuous. The speech has more substance. The speaker makes a more active effort to produce speech.</p>					

	OVERALL PROFICIENCY (overall oral production)	Range	Accuracy	Fluency	Pronunciation
A2	Can describe simple and routine matters related to familiar everyday situations.	Can describe their family, living conditions, educational background and employment situation. Can describe people, places and objects in simple terms. Can describe their hobbies and express what they can do in relation to them. Can briefly describe what they plan to do at the weekend or during the holidays.	Can use basic sentence patterns and some simple structures correctly, but still systematically makes basic mistakes.	Can construct phrases on familiar topics with sufficient ease to handle short exchanges, despite very noticeable and common hesitations and false starts.	Pronunciation is generally clear enough to be understood, but conversational partners will need to ask for repetition from time to time. A strong influence from the other language(s) they speak on stress, rhythm and intonation may affect intelligibility, requiring collaboration from interlocutors. Nevertheless, pronunciation of familiar words is clear.
A2+	Can describe and exchange ideas and information on familiar topics in predictable everyday situations.	Can describe and compare everyday aspects of their environment, e.g., people, places, work or a study experience. Can give short descriptions of future plans and past activities. Can explain what they like or dislike about something.	Can use basic sentence patterns and many simple structures correctly, but still makes mistakes.	Can make themselves understood in short contributions, even though pauses, false starts and reformulation are very evident.	Pronunciation is mostly intelligible, even though the an accent is noticeable and there are challenges with pronunciation.
A2 > B1: Can take the initiative and produce coherent speech independently. Can argue and justify their views in greater detail. The range of language use situations is broader.					

	OVERALL PROFICIENCY (overall oral production)	Range	Accuracy	Fluency	Pronunciation
B1	Can give straightforward descriptions on a variety of topics that are familiar, of personal interest or pertinent to everyday life (e.g., family, hobbies, work, travel and current events).	Can reasonably fluently describe events, real or imagined. Can also give some detailed information.	Uses reasonably accurately a repertoire of frequently used “routines” and patterns associated with more predictable situations.	Can keep going comprehensibly, even though pausing for grammatical and lexical planning and repair is very evident, especially in longer stretches of free production.	Pronunciation is generally intelligible. Can approximate intonation and stress at both utterance and word levels. However, accent is usually influenced by the other language(s) they speak.
B2	Can give clear, detailed descriptions and presentations on a wide range of subjects related to their field of interest, expanding and supporting ideas with subsidiary points and relevant examples.	Has a sufficient range of language to give clear descriptions and express viewpoints on most general topics, without much conspicuous searching for words. Uses some complex sentence forms.	Shows a relatively high degree of grammatical control. Does not make errors that cause misunderstanding, and can correct most of their mistakes.	Can produce continuous speech quite fluently, although can be hesitant in searching for suitable patterns and expressions. There are few noticeably long pauses.	Can generally use appropriate intonation, place stress correctly and articulate individual sounds clearly. Accent tends to be influenced by the other language(s) they speak but has little or no effect on intelligibility.
Exceeds the B2 proficiency level.					

Adapted from the following sources:

CEFR Companion volume, 2020: <https://rm.coe.int/common-european-framework-of-reference-for-languages-learning-teaching/16809ea0d4>

- Overall proficiency: Overall oral production, 62 & Overall oral interaction, 72
- Range: Sustained monologue: describing experience, 63 & General linguistic range, 130
- Accuracy: Grammatical accuracy, 132
- Fluency: Fluency, 142
- Pronunciation: Phonological control, 135

Assessment criteria for the final test of the integration training (not available publicly)

- Descriptions when moving from one skill level to another

Finnish National Agency for Education, Language proficiency level scale: https://www.oph.fi/sites/default/files/documents/kielitaidon_tasojen_kuvausasteikko.pdf

- Used in the descriptions of fluency and pronunciation of the pre-A1 level, as well as in the descriptions of accuracy and pronunciation at the A2+ level.

Translated into English for publication purposes.